

CHEMICAL STUDIES OF SOME INDIAN LAURACEAE FATS. PART II.
THE FATTY OIL FROM THE SEEDS OF *CINNAMOMUM*
CAMPHORA NEES.

By S. A. NARANG AND S. V. PUNTAMBEKAR

The fat from the seeds of *Cinnamomum camphora* Nees. has been found to contain the glycerides of lauric, capric and oleic acids together with a small quantity of unsaponifiable matter.

Cinnamomum camphora Nees. (N. O. Lauraceae) is a large, handsome, evergreen tree attaining in its natural habitat a height of 100 ft. and a girth of 6 to 8 ft., leaves coraceous shining, 3 to 4 inches long, smelling strongly of camphor when crushed. The chief product of the tree, however, is camphor, used largely in the manufacture of celluloid and smokeless powders and also to some extent in drugs and insectifuge. In Northern India, the leaves are shed round about February-March and in March-April, the trees are covered with masses of pale fragrant leaves. The fruit ripens in October. The fruit is dark green, rather dry, one-seed berry is of about 0.3 inch in diameter and turns black after ripening.

The seeds collected from trees in New Forest, Dehra Dun, have been reported to yield 59.0% of a pale yellow fat on kernels and it has been studied for its physico-chemical constants by Puntambekar (this *Journal, Ind. & News Ed.*, 1938, 1, 21). The preliminary studies on this fat have also been reported by Sekimoto and Hirao (*J. Oil Chem. Soc., Japan*, 2, 4) and Tsujimoto (*J. Coll. Eng., Tokyo*, 1908, 4, 75). It was therefore thought desirable to record the results of a detailed examination of this fat.

EXPERIMENTAL

The sample of the fat used in the present investigation was old and had been in storage since 1938; therefore, some variations in acid, iodine and saponification values from that of the fresh fat have been recorded.

TABLE I

Physico-chemical characteristics of the fat.

	Values obtained by		Values obtained by		
	Present authors.	Puntambekar.	Present authors.	Puntambekar.	
Colour	Pale yellow	Pale yellow	Acid value	16.3	14
M. P.	25-26°	...	Sapon. value	299.93	272.3
Sp gr. at 25°	0.924	0.925	Ester value	283.0	270.9
Ref. index at 25°	1.4444	1.4442	Hebner value	88.45%	...
I. V. (Hanus)	3.6	4.0	Unsap. matter	1.4	...

The component fatty acids from *Cinnamomum camphora*, Nees, fat have been quantitatively separated by Twitchell's modified lead-salt method (Hilditch, "The Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats", 1949, p. 468) into groups consisting mainly of saturated and unsaturated acids respectively, followed by conversion of each group into methyl esters, and their systematic fractionation under vacuum. The results obtained are: mean M. W., 195.0; neutralisation value, 286.0; I. V. (Hanus), 3.87; 'solid acids', 46.15% and 'liquid acids', 53.85%.

The fat (92.0 g.) was saponified with alcoholic potash. The alcohol was distilled off, the resultant soap dissolved in water and the mixed acids were liberated by the addition of HCl (conc.). The free fatty acids were washed with warm water and neutralised with 10% KOH solution. The soap solution was concentrated, incorporated with washed filter paper pulp and the resulting soap was dried, powdered and extracted with ether in a soxhlet to remove unsaponifiable matter. The mixed fatty acids (80.0 g) were liberated from the residual soap and 78.0 g. of these was separated into 'solid and liquid acids' by the well-known Twitchell's modified method (Hilditch, *loc. cit.*).

Solid Acids.—The 'solid acids' (26.0 g) were converted into methyl esters in the usual manner by treating with 3% methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid. After distilling off most of the methyl alcohol, the esters were washed with 5% Na₂CO₃ and finally with distilled water. After drying under vacuum, the esters (25.0 g.) were distilled at 4 mm pressure to the following fractions (Table II).

TABLE II

Fraction.	B. P.	Net wt.	Sap. equiv.	I. V.	Methyl laurate.
S ₁	115-120°	1.1865 g.	213.0	1.2	1.1865 g
S ₂	120-125°	11.9774	214.0	1.2	11.9774
S ₃	125-130°	8.4920	215.1	1.3	8.4920
S ₄	130-135°	2.1490	216.0	1.3	2.1490
Residue	...	1.0240	...	...	1.0240
Loss	...	0.1711	...	...	...
Total	...	25.000	...	...	24.8269

All these fractions were saponified separately and the corresponding acids were liberated and these were fractionally crystallised from dilute alcohol and acetone.

Acids from fraction S₁ had the mean M.W. of 200.1 and m.p. 43-44°. These were identified as lauric acid by its mixed melting point with an authentic sample of lauric acid.

Acids from fraction S₂ had the mean M.W. of 201.4 and m. p. 43°. These were identified as lauric acid by its mixed melting point with an authentic sample of lauric acid.

Similarly, the acids obtained from the fractions S₃ and S₄ were identified as lauric acid and the mother-liquors from the above crystallisation of the acids left on evaporation a very little residue which did not show the presence of any other acids.

Liquid Acids.—Methyl esters of the liquid acids were prepared in the usual manner and 37.0 g. of these was fractionated at 4 mm pressure to the following fractions (Table III).

TABLE III

Fraction.	B. P.	Net wt.	I. V.	Sap. equiv.	Component methyl esters.		
					Caprate.	Laurate.	Oleate.
L ₁	100-110°	1.5606 g.	1.0	190.0	1.306 g.	0.2546 g.	...
L ₂	110-120°	4.1755	1.1	199.0	2.030	2.1455	...
L ₃	120-130°	8.7575	1.1	201.0	3.731	5.0265	...
L ₄	130-140°	12.1450	1.1	214.0	...	12.1450	...
L ₅	140-150°	6.5750	22.3	230.0	...	4.9250	1.650 g.
L ₆	150-160°	3.2790	42.1	240.0	...	1.9790	1.300
Residue	...	3.3210	...	...	...	0.1710	0.150
Loss	...	0.1864	...	...	...	...	...
Total	...	37.00...	...	...	7.067	26.5465	3.100

The above fractions were saponified and the corresponding acids were examined separately.

Acids from fraction L₁ had the mean M. W. 176.0 and were liquid. This showed the presence of some acid with a molecular weight lower than that of lauric acid, possibly *ter* capric acid.

Acids from L₂ had the mean M.W. 185.4, thus showing the presence of some lower molecular weight acid. This was separated by the fractional distillation of the mixed acids from the above mentioned fraction. The fraction of the acids which distilled at 266-69° was collected separately and this was refractionated to get a pure sample of the acid (b. p. 268-269°). There was no other fraction which distilled below this temperature, thus showing the absence of *n*-octanoic and hexanoic acids. The molecular weight of the acid of b.p. 268-69° was found to be 171.4 by silver salt method (Clarke, "A Handbook of Organic Analysis", 1949, 4th Ed., p. 315) and identified as capric acid (M.W. calc. 172.0).

The residual acid (m. p. 43-44°) was identified as lauric acid by crystallisation from dilute alcohol and dilute acetone and finding out its mixed melting point with an authentic sample of lauric acid which remained unchanged.

Similarly capric acid was also separated from fraction L₃ by the above mentioned method and confirmed by its mean M.W. 171.3 by the silver salt method. The solid acid in the residue was identified as lauric acid by crystallisation from dilute alcohol and dilute acetone and by mixed m. p. with an authentic sample of lauric acid, m.p. 43-44°.

Acids from the fractions L₄, L₅ and L₆ had the mean M.W. 200.1, 216.0 and 216.1 respectively. These were crystallised from dilute alcohol and dilute acetone and the solid acid melting at 43-44° was found to be lauric acid which was identified by its mixed m. p. with an authentic sample.

Evaporation of the solvent from the mother-liquors from the fractions L₄, L₅ and L₆ yielded a liquid residue in each case and showed the iodine absorption which indicated the presence of an unsaturated acid. The unsaturated acid was oleic acid which was confirmed by carrying out the oxidation of the potassium salt of residual acids from the fractions L₄, L₅ and L₆ in cold alkaline solution with dilute potassium permanganate

by Lapworth and Mottram's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1628). From the resultant acids dihydroxystearic acid, m. p. 130-131°, mean M. W. 318.0, was isolated. This confirmed the presence of oleic acid.

The above data calculated as per example recorded in Part I (this *issue*, p. 139) gave the following components in the mixed fatty acids: lauric acid, 83.89%; capric acid, 10.08%; oleic acid, 4.56% and unsaponifiable matter, 1.47%.

Unsaponifiable Matter.—The unsaponifiable matter was found to be mainly consisting of waxes, hydrocarbons, higher alcohol and a very minute quantity of sterol, but the amount of it was too small for further examination.

Sincere thanks of the authors are due to Dr. Sadgopal, Senior Research Officer-in charge, Chemistry of Forest Products Branch, Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun, for the keen interest he has taken during the investigation and also to the President, F.R.I. and Colleges, Dehra Dun, for allowing the facilities to one of the authors (S.A.N.) for this work to be carried out in this Institute.

CHEMISTRY OF FOREST PRODUCTS BRANCH,
FOREST RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
DEHRA DUN.

Received February 1, 1956.